

Abstract:

The study on "Impact of Training on Employees Efficiency of Daftari Agro Pvt. Ltd., Seloo, Dist. Wardha" analyzed the training policies and sources utilized by the company, identified areas for improvement in training effectiveness, critically evaluated the functioning of the training process, assessed employee and managerial satisfaction levels regarding the training and measured the impact of training on employees efficiency. The research was conducted during the 2023-2024 period, with a sample size of 50 employees. The methodology used included quantitative analysis using percentage, average, and Likert scale tools to assess employees perceptions and satisfaction.

The training data shows that 76 per cent of employees became more efficient after training, with 84 per cent achieving their goals. Skill development was evident in 92 per cent of employees, and 84 per cent reported improvement through HR-provided training. However, areas for improvement included training content (24 per cent), trainer expertise (20 per cent), and frequency (22 per cent). Employees rated training methods (4.38/5) and programs (4.36/5) highly, while HR support was rated lower (4.04/5). Managers expressed satisfaction with overall improvements (4.78/5) and post-training performance (4.44/5). The training impact on job efficiency was rated excellent by 68 per cent of employees, and 84 per cent of HR representatives saw positive changes in job performance. Confidence in task execution post-training was high, with 96 per cent of employees feeling confident, and 92 per cent noted improved team collaboration.

The study highlights the positive impact of on-the-job training on employee performance and emphasizes the importance of continuous improvement in training programs to further enhance employee satisfaction, efficiency, and overall organizational success.

Keywords: Training, Impact, Effectiveness, Efficiency, Performance.

Introduction and Objectives:

Human Resource Management (HRM) plays a crucial role in the development and growth of an organization, and one of its most vital functions is training and development. As defined by Dale S. Beach, "Training is the organized procedure by which people learn knowledge and skills for a definite purpose." Organizations invest heavily in training and development to augment their productivity by enhancing employees' skills and knowledge, which ultimately contributes to the company's success. Since it is difficult to consistently recruit fully skilled individuals, organizations like Daftari Agro Pvt. Ltd. focus on training their workforce to meet both current and future demands. This study focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of training programs at Daftari Agro Pvt. Ltd., based in Seloo, Wardha, Maharashtra. The research investigates employees' views on the effectiveness of the company's training efforts, identifying areas where training can be improved to enhance employee performance.

Daftari Agro Pvt. Ltd. is a key player in the agribusiness sector, specializing in the production of high-quality seeds for crops like cotton, maize, and soybeans. The company's success is heavily reliant on a well-trained workforce capable of reducing waste, enhancing job performance, and contributing to higher productivity. This study explores how training programs at Daftari Agro can be optimized to improve job satisfaction and employee productivity, ultimately supporting the company's growth and efficiency.

The following objectives were selected for the study:

- 1) To identify the probable area of improvement to make training more effective.

- 2) To study satisfaction level of employees as well as managerial level.

- 3) To assess the impact of training on employees efficiency.

Materials and Methods:

The study involved both primary and secondary data collection. Primary data was gathered through interviews and interactions with employees, HR personnel, and company visits. Secondary data was obtained from company reports, records, and personnel management systems. The study was conducted during the period 2023-2024. A purposive sample of 50 employees from various organizational levels at Daftari Agro Pvt. Ltd. was selected. The data was analyzed using statistical tools like percentages, averages, and simple tabular representation. Additionally, a 5-point Likert scale was used to assess employee satisfaction with training, with responses ranging from "Very Dissatisfied" to "Very Satisfied." The data was statistically analyzed by calculating the mean scores for each statement, which were then ranked accordingly.

Results and Discussions:

The resulted data related to the employees' impact toward organization, obtained after training are presented and discussed in logical sequence as follows:

Probable area of improvement to make training more effective**Efficiency of employees after training in job**

Table 1 represents the majority of respondents 76 per cent i.e 38 respondents reported increased efficiency after training, indicating successful program outcomes. However, 24 per cent i.e 12 respondents reported lower efficiency. Overall, the majority of respondents 76 per cent reported being efficient after training. However, 24 per cent of respondents reported being less efficient.

Table 1. Efficiency of employees after training in job

Sr. No	Efficiency	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Efficient (61-100 per cent)	38	76.00
2	Not efficient (Less than 60)	12	24.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 76.01			

Employees achievement of target / goal after training

Table 2 represents A significant majority of respondents, 84 per cent i.e 42 respondents, reported achieving their targets and goals 61-100 per

cent after completing the training. However, 16 per cent i.e 8 respondents reported not achieving their targets and goals less than 60 per cent.

Table 2. Employees achievement of target / goal after training

Sr. No	Target/ goal achievement	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
2	Not achieved (Less than 60)	8	16.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 79.19			

Skill Improvement after Training

Table 3 represents a significant majority of 46 respondents i.e 92 per cent, reported improved skills 61-100 per cent after completing the training.

However, 4 respondents i.e 8 per cent reported not improving their skills less than 60 per cent.

Table 3. Employees skill Improvement after Training

Sr. No	Skill improvement	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
2	No (Less than 60)	4	08.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 84.02			

Employee Skill Improvement after Training provided by HR Department**Table 4. Employees Skill Improvement after Training provided by HR Department**

Sr. No.	Skill improvement	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Yes (61-100 per cent)	42	84.00
2	No (Less than 60)	8	16.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 78.22			

Table 4 represents a significant majority of 42 respondents i.e 84 per cent, as reported by the HR department, indicated improved skills 61- 100 per cent after completing the training. However, 16 per cent of respondents, as reported by the HR department, indicated not improving their skills less than 60 per cent.

training effectiveness: 24 per cent i.e 12 respondents highlighted the need for improved training content, 16 per cent i.e 8 respondents suggested adjusting the duration of training, 20 per cent i.e 10 respondents emphasized enhancing trainer expertise, 22 per cent i.e 11 respondents recommended increasing the frequency of training sessions, and 18 per cent i.e 9 respondents are for reevaluating training methods.

Areas for improvement after training

A survey of 50 respondents identified several key areas for enhancing

Table 5. Areas for improvement after Training

Sr. No	Area of improvement	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Training content	12	24.00
2	Duration of Training	8	16.00
3	Trainer expertise	10	20.00
4	Frequency of Training	11	22.00
5	Training method	9	18.00
	Total	50	100.00

Employees improvements required after Training provide by HR department

The table 6 represents the improvement required after training. The result revealed that 14 respondents agree with improvement in technical related to job function i.e. 28 per cent. 18 respondents agree with the

communication between team or department i.e 36 per cent. 6 respondents said that Improvement in adoption of new technology i.e. 12 per cent. 4 respondents i.e. 8 per cent agree improvement should in time management and productivity.

Table 6. Employees improvements required after Training provided by HR department

Sr. No	Employees area of improvement	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Technical skills related to job functions	14	28.00
2	Communication between teams or departments	18	36.00
3	Leadership or Supervisory skills	6	12.00
4	Adoption of new technologies	8	16.00
5	Time management and Productivity	4	08.00
	Total	50	100.00

Satisfaction level of employee as well as managerial level

Satisfaction level of employee level

Table 7 Employees level of satisfaction towards training

Table 7 represents Employees are most satisfied with the training methods used, with a mean score of 4.38, ranking it first.

Sr. No	Statement of satisfaction levels (Through Likert scale)	Mean score	Ranked based on mean score
1	Training programs provided by the company	4.36	II
2	Support of HR department regarding Training	4.04	VI
3	Training methods (e.g., On the job Training, Off the Training) used	4.38	I
4	Quality of Training provided	4.32	V
5	Management support for Training and employee development	4.34	III
6	Available Training resources and facilities	4.24	V

2) Satisfaction level of manager towards employees after training

Table 8 presents the results of a survey conducted to assess the satisfaction level of managers toward employees after training programs.

The survey utilized a Likert scale to measure manager's opinions on various aspects of employee performance and behaviour after training.

Table 8. Satisfaction level of manager towards employees after training

Sr. No	Statement of satisfaction levels (Through Likert scale)	Mean score	Ranked based on mean score
1	Engagement of the trainee during the sessions	4.04	III
2	Employee performance after Training	4.44	II
3	Overall improvements of employees	4.78	I

III. Impact of training on employees efficiency

1) Training impact on work efficiency

Table 9 represents that training impact on work efficiency. 34 respondents i.e. 68 per cent agree with training impact is excellent on

work efficiency. 9 respondents i.e 18 per cent agree with training impact in good in work efficiency. 7 respondents i.e 14 per cent agree with training impact in average in work efficiency. The average impact of training on work efficiency is to all over employees is 85.32 per cent.

Table 9. Training impact on work efficiency

Sr. No	Training impact	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Excellent (80-100 per cent)	34	68.00
2	Good (60-79 per cent)	9	18.00
3	Average (40-59 per cent)	7	14.00
4	Poor (Less than 39 per cent)	0	00.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 85.32			

Impact of Training on Overall Job Performance expressed by HR department

Table 10 represents the data of impact of training on overall job performance. 42 respondents i.e 84 per cent agree with excellent impact in overall job performance. 5 respondents i.e 10 per cent respondents

agree with good impact on overall job performance. 3 respondents i.e 6 per cent respondents agree with the average impact of training on overall job performance. The overall average training impact on job performance is 85.02 per cent.

Table 10. Impact of Training on Overall Job Performance expressed by HR department

Sr. No	Ratings	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Excellent (80-100 per cent)	42	84.00
2	Good (60-79 per cent)	5	10.00
3	Average (40-59 per cent)	3	6.00
4	Poor (Less than 39 per cent)	0	00.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 85.02			

Employees Rating of Training Impact on Job Performance expressed by HR Department

Table 11 represents the employee rating of training impact on job performance by HR department. For 33 respondents i.e 66 per cent give Grade I for training impact on job performance. For 9 respondents i.e 18

per cent gives Grade II. For 8 respondents i.e 16 per cent give Grade III for impact of training on job performance of employees. Overall, the average of impact of training on job performance of employees is 81.08 per cent.

Table 11. Employees Rating of Training Impact on Job Performance expressed by HR Department

Sr. No	Employees ratings	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Grade I (80-100 per cent)	33	66.00
2	Grade II (60-79 per cent)	9	18.00

3	Grade III (40-59)	8	16.00
4	Grade IV (Less than 39 per cent)	0	00.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 81.08			

Confidence in Task Execution After Training provided by HR department

Table 12 represents the data provided by HR personnels of confidence in task execution after training. 43 respondents i.e 86 per cent are able

to do completely task done after training. 7 respondents i.e 14 per cent respondents are moderately task done after training. No respondents are doing lowest task after training.

Table 12. Confidence in Task Execution After Training expressed by HR department

Sr.No	Task execution	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Completely task done	43	86.00
2	Moderately task done	7	14.00
3	Lowest task done	0	00.00
	Total	50	100.00

5) Employees Confidence in Task Execution After Training expressed by HR Department

Table 13 represents the data of employee confidence in task execution after training by human resource department. 48 respondents i.e 96 per

cent are confident in task execution after training where 2 respondents i.e 4 per cent are not confident for doing task after training. Overall average of task execution after training is 79.8 per cent.

Table 13. Employees Confidence in Task Execution After Training expressed by HR Department

Sr. No	Employees confidence	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Confident (60-100 per cent)	48	96.00
2	Not confident (less than 59 per cent)	2	04.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 79.8			

Positive Impact of Training on employees for Team Collaboration expressed by HR department

Table 14 represent the data of positive impact of training on employees for team collaboration. 46 respondents i.e 92 per cent are able to positive

impact of training for team collaboration. 4 respondents i.e 8 per cent are not shows positive impact of training on employees. overall the average impact of training on employee's for team collaboration is 81.96 per cent.

Table 14. Positive Impact of Training on employees for Team Collaboration expressed by HR Department

Sr. No	Impact of training	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Positive impact (60-100 per cent)	46	92.00
2	No changes (less than 59 per cent)	04	08.00
	Total	50	100.00
Average 78.66			

Conclusion:

Training Effectiveness and Areas for Improvement: Following the training programs, 76 per cent of employees reported improvements in efficiency, and 84 per cent achieved their target goals. Additionally, 92 per cent of respondents indicated that their skills had improved as a result of training. However, areas for refinement were noted, such as content quality (24 per cent) and trainer expertise (20 per cent). Furthermore, 68 per cent of employees acknowledged strong support from management in facilitating these training programs, which contributed to their effectiveness.

Employee and Managerial level satisfaction: Employee satisfaction with the training methods was high, achieving an average score of 4.38 on a five-point scale. Additionally, employees expressed satisfaction with management's support (4.34) and the quality of the training (4.32).

Training Impact on Work Efficiency: The impact of training on work efficiency was notably positive, with 68 per cent of employees rating it as excellent, 18 per cent as good, and 14 per cent as average. Overall, the training's effect on employee efficiency was rated at 85.32 per cent.

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